

Accessibility and use Behavior of Electronic Resources among Post Graduate Students of Bangalore University Library: A Study

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ABSTRACT: This research paper examine the Accessibility and Use behavior of Electronic resources among Post Graduate students of Bangalore university library . there are 150 Questionnaire distributed to the Post graduate students of Bangalore university out of which 133(88.66%) filled questionnaires were received back from the students these are some objectives of the present study To know the Number of questionnaires distributed and received back To know course wise response received, To find out Gender wise response received, To know Age wise response received, To find out Knowledge on computer literacy, To know Frequency of visit to the library, To know purpose of visit to the library, To know Time spent in library, To find out Use of electronic resources, To know Frequency of use Electronic resources.

KEYWORDS: Accessibility, behavior, Electronic resources, university, questionnaires, gender, response, computer literacy, frequency.

1. INTRODUCTION

Electronic resources are playing very important role in this knowledge environmental era. E-resources are which is available in online and of line mode which are in electronic form such as e-books, e-journals, e-magazines, e-research reports, e-newspapers, e-newsletters, e-databases, e-thesis and Dissertation, CD/DVD-Rom etc. university libraries are providing e-resources to faculty members, students, Research scholars, teachers, and also for research purpose. electronic resources are comes under different formats including text, image, videos, audio, maps, graphics, tables, pictures etc.

1.1 About Bangalore university :

Bangalore University is located in the Garden City of Bangalore it was established in July 1964 as an off shoot of the University of Mysore, the University introduced Honours Courses in the year 1965-66. Three year Honour's courses in Botany, Chemistry, Economics, English, Geology, Kannada, Mathematics and Zoology which were offered only at the University Post Graduate Departments have attracted many brilliant students. Honours passed students were admitted to Post Graduate Courses on priority and B.A./B.Sc. graduates. Since 1964, Bangalore University has grown both in size and strength to include a large number of affiliated colleges, P.G. Centers with a rich diversity of programme options. In consonance with this expansion, in 1973, the University moved into a new campus named 'Jnana Bharathi' (JB) located on a sprawling 1100 acres of land and shifted many of its post graduate departments to this newly established campus

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Kwafoa and others (2019) They examine in their research paper Survey methodology was adopted for this study, the findings revealed that awareness was high 138 (34.5%) were aware of OPAC, 149 (37.3%) were aware of Academic Databases whilst 93 (23.2%) were aware of Dspace. 78 (19.5%) of the respondents got to know of them from notices on campus, 63 (15.8%) through flyers, 67 (16.7%) through radio adverts, 26 (6.5%) through newsletters, 43 (10.8%) through posters and 123 or 30.7% through UCC library guide. 266 (66.5%) said the library had provided training on the use of OPAC while 134 (33.5%) said the library had not provided training on use of OPAC. Also, 292 (73.0%) said the library had provided training on the use of Academic databases while 108 (27.0%) said the library had not provided training on using academic databases. Again, 273 (68.3%) said the library had provided training on the use of Dspace. **Anhwere and Paulina (2018)** examine in their research paper the Survey method adopted for the study majority of the respondents that is 205 (51.2%) access electronic resources both on and off campus, and only 138 (34.5%) access their electronic resources on campus. Again, only 57 (14.3%) access theirs off campus. 68%

Accessibility and use Behavior of Electronic Resources among Post Graduate Students of Bangalore University Library: A Study

or 275 respondents indicated electronic resources access on campus as good compare to 30 (9.6%) who indicated access off campus as good. 351 (87.8%) of the respondents indicated useful in the use of academic database whilst 49 (12.2%) indicated otherwise. Also, 269 (67.2%) stated the usefulness of Dspace as compared to 131 (32.8%) who stated otherwise. Again, 150 (37.5%) of the respondents agreed that the OPAC is useful whilst the majority 250 (62.5%) of the respondents disagreed. **Kashyap (2017)** This Study based on Survey Method. The finding reveal that Majority of P.G. students use e- resource for study purpose and least numbers of students use e- resource for seminar presentation. 70.64 % Students are satisfied with Use of e-resources. 16.91 % very satisfied, 5.97 % dissatisfied and 6.46 % are unsure about satisfaction level. also found that majority (34.23%) of the P.G. students spends 1-2 hours in a week and least number of the Students (5.97%) spends 4-5 hours in week for e- resources.

3. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

- To know the Number of questionnaires distributed and received back
- To know course wise response received
- To find out Gender wise response received
- To know Age wise response received
- To find out Knowledge on computer literacy
- To know Frequency of visit to the library
- To know purpose of visit to the library
- To know Time spent in library
- To find out Use of electronic resources
- To know Frequency of use Electronic resources
- To find out Awareness of electronic resources
- To know benefits of using e-resources
- To find out separate section for accessing e-resources
- To know overall Satisfaction of electronic resources

4. SCOPE AND LIMITATIONS AND METHOD OF THE STUDY

The present study limited only PG students of Bangalore university Library, Bangalore. The Survey method adopted for study there are 150 questionnaires distributed and 133(88.66%) filled questionnaires were received back from the students.

5. DATA ANALYSIS

The collected data was analyzed and presented with tables and graphs

Table 1. Number of questionnaires distributed and received back

No .of Questionnaires distributed	N. of questionnaires received back	%
150	133	88.66

T 1 shows that Number of questionnaires distributed and received back from Post Graduate students of Bangalore University. There are 150 Questionnaire were distributed and 133(88.66%) are received back.

Fig. 1 Number of questionnaires distributed and received back

Accessibility and use Behavior of Electronic Resources among Post Graduate Students of Bangalore University Library: A Study

Table 2. course wise response received

Sl. No	Course	No. of respondents	%
1	MA	49	36.84
2	MSc	46	34.58
3	Mcom	38	28.58
Total		133	100

T 2 shows that course wise response received from the students. There are 49(36.84%) studying MA followed by 46(34.58%) are MSc and 38(28.58%) are studying Mcom .

Fig.2 course wise response received.

Table 3. Gender wise response received

Sl. No	Gender	No. of respondents	%
1	Male	60	45.11
2	Female	73	54.89
Total		133	100

T3 shows that Gender wise response received from the students there are 60(45.11%) are male students and 73(54.89%) are Female.

Fig.3 Gender wise response received.

Table 4. Age wise response received

Sl. No	Age	No. of respondents	%
1	21-23	43	32.33
2	24-26	35	26.31
3	27-30	33	24.81
4	31 and above	22	16.55
Total		133	100

Accessibility and use Behavior of Electronic Resources among Post Graduate Students of Bangalore University Library: A Study

T4 shows that Age wise response received there are 43(32.33%) are between the age group of 21-23 years followed by 35(26.31%) are between the age group of 24-26, 33(24.81%) are between the age group of 27-30 Years and 22(16.55%) are between the age group of 31 and above.

Fig.4 Age wise response received

Table 5. Knowledge on computer literacy

Sl. No	Computer literacy	No. of respondents	%
1	Yes	133	100
2	No	Nil	000
Total		133	100

T5 shows that Knowledge on computer literacy there are 133(100%) are having knowledge on use of computers.

Table 6. Frequency of visit to the library

Sl. No	Frequency	No. of respondents	%
1	Every Day	44	33.08
2	Once in a week	26	19.55
3	Two times in a week	25	18.79
4	Once in a month	19	14.29
5	Rarely	19	14.29
Total		133	100

T6 Shows that Frequency of visit to the library there are 44(33.08%) were visit library Every Day followed by 26(19.55%) were visit library Once in a week, 25(18.79%) were visit their library Two times in a week, 19(14.29%) were visit library Once in a month and 19(14.29%) were visit library Rarely.

Fig. 5 Frequency of visit to the library

Accessibility and use Behavior of Electronic Resources among Post Graduate Students of Bangalore University Library: A Study

Table 7. Purpose of visit to the library

Sl. No	purpose	No. of respondents	%
1	To issue/return of the books	47	35.33
2	To access internet	23	17.29
3	To complete assignment	19	14.29
4	For research work	13	09.78
5	To use e-resources	14	10.53
6	For Xerox/print out	17	12.78
Total		133	100

T7 Shows that purpose of visit to the library there are 47(35.33%) were visit library for the purpose To issue/return of the books followed by 23(17.29%) were visit library for the purpose of To access internet, 19(14.29%) were visit library To complete assignment, 13(09.78%) were visit library For research work, 14(10.53%) were visit library To use e-resources and 17(12.78%) were visit library For Xerox/print out only.

Fig.6 purpose of visit to the library

Table 8. Time spent in library

Sl. No	Time	No. of respondents	%
1	1 to 2 hours	39	29.33
2	2 to 3 hours	35	26.32
3	3 to 4 hours	31	23.30
4	4 hours and above	28	21.05
Total		133	100

T8 shows that Time spent in library there are 39(29.33%) were Spent 1 to 2 hours time in library followed by 35(26.32%) were spent 2-3 hours time, 31(23.30%) were spent 3-4 hours time, 28(21.05%) were spent 4 hours and above in library.

Fig.7 Time spent in library

Table 9. Use of electronic resources

Sl. No	Use of e-resources	No. of respondents	%
1	Yes	133	100
2	No	Nil	000
Total		133	100

T 9 shows that Use of electronic resources there are 133(100%) were using electronic resources in their library.

Table 10. Frequency of use Electronic resources

Sl. No	Frequency	No. of respondents	%
1	Daily	41	30.83
2	Once in a week	37	27.81
3	Two times in a week	31	23.30
4	Three times in a week	11	08.28
5	Once in a month	13	09.78
Total		133	100

T 10 Shows that Frequency of use Electronic resources there are 41(30.83%) were Daily visit library to use Electronic resources followed by 37(27.81%) visit library Once in a week, 31(23.30%) were visit library Two times in a week, 11(08.28%) were visit library Three times in a week, 13(09.78%) were visit library Once in a month.

Fig.8 Frequency of use Electronic resources

Accessibility and use Behavior of Electronic Resources among Post Graduate Students of Bangalore University Library: A Study

Table 11. Awareness of electronic resources (Responded more than one option)

Sl. No	e- resources	No. of respondents	%
1	e-Books	120	90.22
2	e-journals	110	82.70
3	e-theses/ e-dissertations	121	90.97
4	e-Newspapers	133	100
5	CD ROMs/DVDs	133	100
6	Search engines	115	86.46

T11 shows that Awareness of electronic resources. There are 120(90.22%) were aware of Electronic Books followed by 110(82.70%) were aware of Electronic Journals 121 (90.97%) were aware of e-theses/ e-dissertations, 133(100%) were of e-Newspapers, 133(100%) were aware of CD ROMs/DVDs and 115(86.46%) were aware of Search engines.

Fig.9 Awareness of electronic resources

Table 12. Benefits of using e-resources (Responded more than one option)

Sl. No	Benefits	No. of respondents	%
1	Up to date knowledge	098	73.68
2	Faster information access	110	82.70
3	Access other e-resources	89	66.91
4	Save the time	130	97.74
5	Easy to read	127	95.48

T12 shows that benefits of using e-resources there are 98(73.68%) were using for Up to date knowledge followed by 110(82.70%) were using for Faster information access, 89(66.91%) were Access other e-resources, 130 (97.74%) were Save the time and 127(95.48%) were using electronic resources to Easy to read.

Fig.10 benefits of using e-resources

Table 13. separate section for accessing e-resources

Sl. No	Separate Section	No. of respondents	%
1	Yes	133	100
2	No	Nil	000
Total		133	100

T 13 Shows that separate section for accessing e-resources there are 133(100%) were responded that they are having separate section for accessing e-resources.

Table 14. Overall Satisfaction of electronic resources

Sl. No	Satisfaction	No. of respondents	%
1	satisfied	83	62.40
2	Partially satisfied	43	32.33
3	Not satisfied	07	05.27
Total		133	100

T14 shows that overall Satisfaction of electronic resources there are 83(62.40%) were Satisfied with e-resources followed by 43(32.33%) were Partially satisfied and 07(05.27%) were Not satisfied.

Fig.11 overall Satisfaction of electronic resources

Accessibility and use Behavior of Electronic Resources among Post Graduate Students of Bangalore University Library: A Study

6. FINDINGS AND CONCLUSION OF PRESENT STUDY

The major findings of the study revealed that There are 150 Questionnaire were distributed and 133(88.66%) are received back from the students followed by 49(36.84%) studying MA, 46(34.58%) are MSc and 38(28.58%) are studying Mcom, 60(45.11%) are male students and 73(54.89%) are Female, 43(32.33%) are between the age group of 21-23 years 35(26.31%) are between the age group of 24-26, 33(24.81%) are between the age group of 27-30 Years and 22(16.55%) are between the age group of 31 and above, 44(33.08%) were visit library Every Day, 26(19.55%) were visit library Once in a week, 25(18.79%) were visit their library Two times in a week, 19(14.29%) were visit library Once in a month and 19(14.29%) were visit library Rarely, 47(35.33%) were visit library for the purpose To issue/return of the books 23(17.29%) were visit library for the purpose of To access internet,19(14.29%) were visit library To complete assignment,13(9.78%) were visit library For research work, 14(10.53%) were visit library To use e-resources and 17(12.78%) were visit library For Xerox/print out only, 39(29.33%) were Spent 1 to 2 hours time in library, 35(26.32%) were spent 2-3 hours time, 31(23.30%) were spent 3-4 hours time, 28(21.05%) were spent 4 hours and above in library.

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